

DISKSIMON ISHCHI ORGANLAR KONSTRUKSIYALARI TAHLILI

Rashidov Nurbek Shermamat o'g'li

dotsent. Qarshi muhandislik-iqtisodiyot instituti, Qarshi, O'zbekiston Respublikasi

Annotasiya: *Disksimon ishchi organlarning bir necha xil turlari ma'lum bo'lib, ular tuproqqa ishlov berish mashinalarida keng qo'llaniladi. disksimon ishchi organni uzlukli ariqlar va o'rkachlar hosil qilish uchun qo'llab bo'lmaydi, chunki u o'tgandan so'ng har xil balandlikdagi o'rkachlar yuzaga keladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *nishabli, disk, o'rkachlar, uzlukli ariqlar, sferik disk, balandlik.*

JUSTIFICATION OF THE OPTIMAL PARAMETERS OF THE RIPPER

Abstract: *There are several different types of disc working tools that are widely used in tillage machines. the disk-shaped working body cannot be used to create continuous ditches and sickles, since after its passage, sickles of different heights are formed.*

Keywords: *sloping, disc, ducks, continuous ditches, spherical disk, height.*

Kirish. Mamlakatimizda hozirgi kungacha nishabli dalalarga ag'dargichli asosiy ishlov berish bilan birga dala yuzasida o'rkachlar va uzlukli ariqlar hamda ariqlarda to'siqlar hosil qilish texnologiyasi va uni amalga oshiradigan pluglarni ishlab chiqish, ular tomonidan bajariladigan texnologik jarayonlarni o'rganish, ishchi qismlarni asoslash bo'yicha yetarli darajada tadqiqotlar o'tkazilmagan.

Tahlil va natijalar: Disksimon ishchi organlarning bir necha xil turlari ma'lum bo'lib, ular tuproqqa ishlov berish mashinalarida keng qo'llaniladi.

Rossiya Federatsiyasida G.P.Balbichev va boshqalar tomonidan [71] aylanish tekisligiga parallel tekislikda periferiya qismi lopast shaklida qilingan disksimon ishchi organ taklif qilingan. Uning har bir lopastining oldingi qirradi radius yo'nalishidan uning aylanish tomoniga qiya qilingan. Lopastning oldingi qirradi siniq chiziq ko'rinishida bo'lib, yuqori qismi 90° ni tashkil qiladi.

Jan-Sharl Javerlyak [72] tomonidan (1-rasm) beshta qabariq lopastga ega bo'lgan va egri qirg'ich bilan jihozlangan sferik disk taklif qilingan. Ushbu disk disksimon pluglarda qo'llanish uchun mo'ljallangan.

1-rasm. RU105108 patent bo'yicha disksimon ishchi organ

2-rasmda keltirilgan disk logarifm spirali shaklida qilingan tishlardan iborat, uning formulasi [72]

$$\rho = \rho_0 q^{\varphi/2\pi}, \quad (1)$$

bunda ρ – logarifmik spiralinig egrilik radiusi, sm;

ρ_0 – boshlang'ich radius, sm;

q – logarifmik spiralinig o'sish koeffitsiyenti;

φ – radius vektorni buralish koeffitsiyenti.

2-rasm. Tishli sferik disk sxemasi

Oldingi va keyingi kesish qirralarining boshlang'ich radiusi va logarifmik spiraling o'sish koeffitsiyenti bir xil. Ushbu diskning kamchiligi shundan iboratki, diskning murakkab shaklini yasash texnologiyasi uni narxini oshirib yuboradi, uning tig'i nostandart bo'lgani uchun charxlash o'ta murakkab.

3-rasm. Disksimon ishchi organ

a – kesik sferik diskning umumiy ko‘rinishi; *b* – A-A – diskning kesimi;

1 – disk; *2* – tishlar; *3* – oldingi kesish qirradi; *4* – orqa kesish qirradi

I.D.Kobyakov tomonidan plug va lushchilnikka o'rnatish uchun oltiburchakli disk ishlab chiqilgan va uning parametrlari asoslangan [73].

4-rasm. Oltiburchakli disk sxemasi

Asosan boronalarda foydalanish uchun G-simon "avs" kesikli ishchi organ (4-rasm) taklif qilingan [73]. Kesiklar disk periferiyasida teng intervallarda joylashgan. Kesik "yev" ning kesadigan qirradi radial bo'yicha joylashgan va diskning markazi *O* dan kesikning chuquri "v" orqali o'tgan to'g'ri chiziq "os" ga tushadi. Ikkinchi kesish qirradi "av" radius "os" kichik burchak < ostida, mos holda kesish qirradi "yeye".

5-rasm. Disksimon boronaning ishchi organi

Ushbu disksimon ishchi organni uzlukli ariqlar va o'rkachlar hosil qilish uchun qo'llab bo'lmaydi, chunki u o'tgandan so'ng har xil balandlikdagi o'rkachlar yuzaga keladi.

XULOSA

O'tkazilgan adabiyotlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, O'zbekiston sharoitida tuproqqa asosiy ishlov berishning mavjud texnologiyalari va texnik vositalari nishabli dalalarga sifatli ishlov berishni to'liq ta'minlamaydi, suv eroziyasi jarayonlarini oldini olmaydi, natijada o'simliklarning hosildorligi va ish unumining pasayishiga olib keladi.

O'tkazilgan adabiyotlar tahliliga ko'ra, nishabli dalalarda suv eroziyasini oldini olishning samarali texnologiyalaridan biri tuproqqa ishlov berish bilan birga shudgor yuzasida o'rkachlar va uzlukli ariqlar hosil qilish hisoblanadi.

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